

Factors Affecting Readers' Satisfaction in "Waspada" Newspapers: Insight from Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The newspaper of "Waspada" is one of the oldest newspapers in the city of Medan and a newspaper that contribute to disseminate information in the provinces of Aceh and North Sumatera. The "Waspada" newspaper has golden age during its time. Today, "Waspada" newspapers have to compete with the digital age, this reflects and results in a decline in readers' loyalty to print media. The present study attempts to explore and identify factors that influence customer satisfaction, especially those that determine the dominant factor in "Waspada" newspaper readers' loyalty. In this study researchers will seek to uncover new theories that can serve as a decisive factor in solving customer loyalty issues. A sample of 180 respondents were selected based on the characteristics of non-probability sampling - purposive sampling. The data analysis model is a stepwise linear regression. The study found five variables that affect satisfaction, including product quality, price, service quality behavior, post-purchase behavior and emotional relationships.

Keywords: Readers satisfaction, Post-purchase behavior, Service quality behavior, Price, Emotional relationship, Waspada newspaper

INTRODUCTION

Communication is an important factor that affects understanding between sender and receiver. Communication becomes a measure of the flow of information spreading or spinning at one point. Today, the science of communication has grown exponentially with many channels in the dissemination of

information. Through many channels used communication creates different perceptions depending on the receiver's interpretation. While the main source of information is informants, it is in anticipation of this that many punctuation marks are used in communicating to provide greater understanding to the receivers. In channel communication, it is necessary to use a form of communication media.

Communication media is a channel created as a means of information exchange, in which the communication media has various regulations and interpretations of each communication statement either positively or negatively. Communication media as a communicator which is also plays a proactive role in interpreting every element of information to avoid misunderstanding and negative thinking. How difficult it is for the media to play a role in refining the flow of information without negative effects. One of the communication mediums we have used for a long time is the newspaper.

Newspapers are paper-based communication media consisting of multiple pages with content settings tailored to each page's segment. In the past, newspapers were only available in major cities and appeared almost twice daily. This means that newspaper printing is always busy and stands by for new information to load and print immediately. Newspapers are also a lifestyle for intellectuals; because there is an analogy with reading that we can see the world. This is what makes newspapers have a special segment in their readers' hearts. In

fact, newspapers have become a trend of successful people in Indonesia. Sumatera in particular, has a famous newspaper called "Waspada".

The newspaper "Waspada" is the oldest newspaper in North Sumatra that is the forerunner of the history of the press struggle in North Sumatra, located in a magnificent building known as "Waspada". Philosophically, readers consider this newspaper to be "more cautious" and remind us readers to always beware of every situation. Nowadays, the growing digital world of newspapers has also released "Waspada" online which has quite a number of active readers.

Reader satisfaction is a good and bad measure of product in meeting customer expectations. "Waspada" newspapers in terms of customer satisfaction are less likely to drive consumers through word of mouth about the reputation of these newspapers, resulting in the "Waspada" newspaper only known to some urban consumers. Although this newspaper is popular in the past, those who enjoy it are only loyal readers of the past.

Product quality is everything that consumers use to measure the eligibility of goods and services. The "Waspada" newspaper that has been able to assess its ability to survive in today's dynamic era is considered to be lacking in ability and underlines the importance of newspapers. That is not apparent to prospective readers, who do not feel moved to read "Waspada" newspaper content, they only know "Waspada" is one of the newspapers in Medan.

Price is everything that consumers sacrifice for goods and services. Today, many newspapers are competing in the communications media market, but it has a positive impact on marketing. For prospective consumers, the price of "Waspada" newspapers is quite expensive and inaccurate when compared to other similar, lower priced newspapers with the same quality of news as the newspaper.

Service behavior is a form of behavior that a company or provider engages in meeting the needs of others. In this case readers feel "Waspada" newspaper is less responsive to the latest issues that headline the other day even on television. Waspada newspapers are considered less capable of providing information faster than other media, despite the fact that the media's role is to convey information rather than fabricate news and even influence public opinion.

Ease of use is a situation where consumers can use the product without the hassle caused by the use or consumption of the product. In terms of usage, readers are wary of being less communicative in communicating news in terms of language usage. The language may only be understood by intellectuals who understand a lot of vocabulary and not for young readers or beginners who consider the language used too high and difficult for the general public to understand.

Consumer decisions are a form of selection that has been decided upon by various alternatives created in the minds of consumers. To understand consumer decisions in this study is the decision of readers of this newspaper who feel less needed as a compulsory reading or reference for their knowledge. Readers judge that in order to be reading, they will need a "Waspada" newspaper, but in this case the reader will not need it.

Post-purchase behavior is a form of behavior that consumers exhibit after the purchase of a product (Decision Effect). In addressing the effects of the decision to read the "Waspada" newspapers, readers prefer reading via the internet over conventional and substituting other news portals. This makes it less capable of competing for consumer preference in today's digital culture.

Emotional connection is a form of feeling created by consumers and companies in the use of the product and lasts for a long time. For the "Waspada" readers who read this newspaper from a

young age, it may have created a strong sense of belonging, but for beginners' readers lacked this sense and very often made the "Waspada" newspaper a secondary knowledge for its reference.

Trust is a form of confidence that consumers place on a product or company. Essentially, "Waspada" newspapers have the confidence of their consumers, but lack the ability to convince potential consumers, teens who are potential readers. For young people, the "Waspada" newspapers are considered less capable of showing their integrity as a youth newspaper.

Consumer attention is a form of concern that companies provide to consumers. The "Waspada" newspapers are very attentive to their readers, seen from the many quizzes they give and prizes in weekly or monthly. During the month of Ramadhan, and the football season, Waspada newspapers are more likely to attract readers, but this is less for readers, as readers hope not only for the quizzes and gifts by the Waspada newspapers.

Accordingly, on the basis of exposure to the above issues the authors are interested in capturing the title factors affecting readers satisfaction in "Waspada" newspapers.

Literature Review

Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a good or bad measure of a product in fulfilment customer expectations.

Factors affecting customer satisfaction.

To determine customer satisfaction, there are five factors that companies should consider (Lupiyoadi, Rambat; Hamdani, 2013) among others:

- Product quality means that customers are satisfied when their results indicate that the products used are qualified.
- The quality of the service or service, that is, the customer will be satisfied when they get the good or expected service.
- Emotionally, customers will feel proud and have confidence that others will admire them when using products with a

particular brand that tend to have a higher level of satisfaction.

- Satisfaction is not due to the quality of the product but the social or self esteem that makes the customer satisfied with the particular brand.
- Pricing, which is a product of the same quality but setting relatively low prices, will provide higher value to customers.
- Cost is that customers who do not have to spend extra or need to waste time getting a product or service tend to be satisfied with the product or service.

Indicators of customer satisfaction including; repurchase; created word of mouth; creating a brand image and make a purchase decision

Product quality

Product quality is everything consumers use to measure the good or bad of a product or service. Products are the product of production that will be presented to consumers to be distributed and used by consumers to meet their needs. Product quality is an attempt to meet or exceed customer expectations where a product has a quality that meets the standards of quality established. Quality is an ever-changing condition because consumers' taste or expectations of a product are constantly changing.

Factors affecting product quality

In the case of quality, a product produced by a company is sometimes subject to diversity, as the quality of a product is influenced by several factors, which factors can influence a product that meets the standards set or not. These factors, among others.

1. Human; The role of the person or employee in the company will have a direct impact on the quality of the product that a company produces. Therefore, the human aspect needs attention. The focus is on training, motivation, well-being, and more.

2. Management; The responsibility for the quality of production within the company is imposed on a group commonly known as the Function Group. In this case the leader should make good coordination between the function group and the other sections of the company. With such coordination, it is possible to achieve a good and harmonious work environment, and to avoid confusion in the workplace. Conditions that allow companies to maintain the quality and improve the quality of the products they produce.
3. Money; Companies need to make enough money to maintain or improve the quality of their products. For instance, maintenance and repair of machinery or production equipment, defective product repair, and more.
4. Raw materials, are one of the most important factors and will affect the quality of the product that a company produces. For this reason, the quality control of raw materials is very important. In the case of raw materials, companies should consider several things: source selection of raw materials, inspection of purchase documents, inspection of raw material acceptance, and storage. These things need to be done well, as it is possible that the raw materials that will be used for the low-quality production process can be suppressed as little as possible.
5. Machines and equipments; The machines and equipment used in the production process will affect the quality of the products produced by the company. Inadequate equipment and outdated also uneconomical machines will result in lower product quality, and lower efficiency. As a result, the cost of production is high, while the products generated are unlikely to be marketable. That will prevent the company from competing against other similar companies, which use automated machines and equipment.

Product quality indicators such as; performance; features; durability; suitability; reliability; ability; aesthetics and perceived quality.

Price

Price is everything that consumers sacrifice for goods and services. Understanding the costs that consumers have to sacrifice, the higher the price of the sacrifice, the less likely it is to decide on a product. But for luxury products that involve consumers' lifestyle, the case is different. The higher the price of the product, the higher the prestige that consumers will have for the product. It depends on the type of product being created and the market-recognized conditions.

Factors affecting prices

Understanding price has many factors, they can be formulated and published to consumers. Each price is determined based on the cost of sacrifice based on segment, target and consumer positioning. The factors that affect prices are as follows:

1. Raw materials prices; is the value that the supplier offers the manufacturer to acquire resources in processing, to convert input into output.
2. Operating costs; is the total cost incurred by the company to determine the total cost that is sacrificed to create one unit of product.
3. The number of workers employed; is a mass of labor used and working together or disconnected in creating, assembling the final process into the hands of consumers.
4. Equipments and tools; an intermediary medium between the change of input to output. Equipments and tools become the medium that works in the process of production
5. Distribution location; the size of the delivery or distribution area of the movement of all resources or products. Distribution locations include the

movement of raw materials to factories, products to retailers, retailers to consumers or better known as supply chain management in support of production processes.

6. Method of work; a way that companies apply to make production process work more effective and efficient.

Price indicator such as price range; competitive pricing (competition); price compatibility with product quality and price compatibility with products.

Service Behavior

Service behavior is a form of behavior that a company or product provider performs to meet the needs of others. These actions will affect consumers' attitudes while enjoying the service of the company.

Factors affecting service behavior

Serving consumers for their product needs, marketers need to look at something else. Consumers need only the product but how to deliver the product and its value to the consumer. It's the foundation that makes the service stand out and must be embraced by marketers. In service to consumers, service behavior is influenced by a number of factors that can have a positive and negative effect on consumers; form of service, service method, service flow, service competence and service uniform.

Indicator of service behavior including; form; responsiveness; guarantee and empathy.

Ease of use

Ease of use is a condition where consumers can use the product without any difficulties caused by the use or consumption of the product.

Factors affecting ease of use.

When a consumer decides to make a purchase, the next step is to use or consume it in the marketing world. Some consumers stop buying and do not use it due to a lack of knowledge on how to use it. Factors affecting consumer behavior are consumer knowledge, consumer competence,

consumer experience with the product, implementation instructions and quick understanding of product operations and interesting and familiar product interactions. Indicators of ease of use such as; learning; flow suitability; communicative and interactive; hotline / operating manual

Consumer decisions

Consumer decisions are a form of selection that has been decided upon by various alternatives created in the minds of consumers.

Factors affecting consumer decisions

When a consumer decides something out of the alternative, the decision falls on a product. The question is whether the choice was made properly, or not at its own discretion. Many studies have shown that consumer decisions are influenced by many factors. Consumer decisions include what they buy, use, and visit. Factors that influence consumer decisions include product, product price, place of transaction, promotion, seller performance, situation, social environment and the consumer's own personality.

Indicators of consumer decisions such as attitude; intention; consumer ability; needs.

Post-purchase behavior.

Post-purchase behavior is a form of behavior that consumers exhibit after the purchase of a product (Decision Effect).

Factors affecting post-purchase behavior.

When a consumer decides to make a purchase, the next step is whether or not the consumer repeats it. Looking at post-purchase consumer behavior, marketers need to understand whether consumer expectations are in line with the value that the product produces. Understanding the change in behavior that consumers make after using the product, it can have a positive or negative impact on their achievement for future decisions. The factors that influence post-purchase behavior are product satisfaction, brand relationship and desire to use more.

Post-purchase behavior indicators such as; perception; motivation; personality and culture.

Emotional relationships

Emotional relationships are a form of feeling created by consumers and companies in the use of the product and lasts for a long time.

Factors affecting emotional relationships.

It has become a necessity; a company that has always existed in the business world should always be competitive and improve its performance. Companies that are not able to compete will fail in their efforts. Many companies are responding to this challenge by building a harmonious relationship with their customers and their suppliers. By establishing a relationship with its customers, it will achieve sustainability in material fulfillment and excellence in the cost efficiency of companies in the production of goods. Companies rely on their commitment and trust in marketing relationships, and the impact of marketing relationships on corporate costs. Factors affecting marketing relationships are commitment, product trust and marketing relationships.

Emotional relationship indicators such as; passions; knowledge; a sense of belonging; customer experience

Consumer trust

Consumer trust is a form of trust that consumers place on a product or company.

Factors affecting consumer trust

In analyzing factors that influence consumer trust in the use of a product. Product image is a guarantee in building trust for consumers. Understanding the consumer's trust in the product is influenced by the following factors:

1. Perceived benefits; is a sense that consumers value in evaluating the benefits of a product in meeting their potential needs.
2. Brand; are all identifiable and may represent the introduction of a product, thereby seeing a brand not covered by name and logo but covering broader

aspects, such as color, specifications, culture, workforce, tagline, and all that mark it.

3. Branding companies; is a body that is a manufacturer or intermediary of brand creation. Sometimes product brand names differ from company name. That is to distinguish it from another brand created by the company in dividing the market by creating another brand.

Consumer trust indicators such as; legality; integrity; goodness; competence

Consumer attention

Consumer attention is a form of concern that companies give to their consumers.

Factors affecting consumer attention

When it comes to retaining consumers, marketing is not a process of product delivery or breakdown once a consumer has purchased it, but rather how to build relationships and keep consumers informed of what they expect in the future. It will be a serious concern as the basis for future product creation. Understanding consumer attention is influenced by several factors:

1. Habits; is something that consumers do in real time and there is a repetition, something that is affecting a consumer's attention to look at or see a product.
2. Stimulation; is an action that may go up or down as a result of the moderation effect on consumers' choice of a product.
3. Needs; a form of compulsory subject matter that consumers must fulfill in order to survive; a consumer will focus on something that is the basis of his or her life, and the consumer's attention sometimes leads to something he or she needs most.
4. Atmosphere; is a condition that the consumer accepts either from within or from outside. The atmosphere has a stronger effect on making consumers aware of the circumstances surrounding them.

Indicators of consumer attention such as; care; expectancy; product value; appreciation

RESEARCH METHODS

The material used in this study is material related to variables that influence customer satisfaction. Many of these research variables are new and will be addressed in this study. The emergence of each variable due to the research, therefore the field research variable will only rotate within the simple variable without development.

Research procedure

The present study basically goes through four main stages, namely the preliminary stage, data analysis, interpretation of data and drawing conclusions. In the early stages, the authors collected all the data that supported the research and observed the phenomena of the problem in the field. Later in the data analysis, the data were analyzed using the impact analysis approach. In the next step, the interpretation of the data, the authors

present and describe the results of our findings based on the preliminary data after the data analysis. In the final stages of interpretation, the authors draw conclusions about the solution of the phenomenon that occurs in the preliminary stage, in other words the conclusion stage will address the research problem and recommend the solution to the relevant parties.

From the presentation of the research material, a conceptual framework was developed which later became the basis for analyzing the research data. starting from customer satisfaction as a dependent variable is influenced by many factors that the author will test, including post-purchase behavior variables, customer emotional relationships, customer trust and attention variables, product quality, cost, service behavior, ease of use, and consumer decision variables.

A conceptual framework developed by the authors (2020)

Hypothesis development

H1. The quality of the product has related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan.

H2. Price has related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan.

H3. The behavior of the service has related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan.

H4. The ease of use has related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan.

H5. Consumers decision have related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan.

H6. Post-purchase behavior has related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan

H7. Emotional relationships have related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan

H8. Consumers trust has related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan

H9. Consumers attention have related to the customer satisfaction in the context of Waspada newspaper in Medan

Operational definition

An operational definition to describe how the format for each indicator represents each variable.

Table 1 Operational definitions

No	Variables	Operational definitions	Indicators	Scale
1	Customer Satisfaction (Y)	Customer satisfaction is a good or bad measure of a product in fulfilment customer expectations	1. Repurchase 2. Created word of mouth 3. Creating a brand image 4. Make a purchase decision	Ordinal
2	Product quality	Product quality is everything consumers use to measure the good or bad of a product or service	1. Performance 2. Features 3. Durability 4. Suitability 5. Reliability 6. Ability 7. Aesthetics 8. Perceived quality	Ordinal
3	Price	Price is everything that consumers sacrifice for goods and services.	1. Price range 2. Competitive pricing 3. Price compatibility with product quality 4. Price compatibility with products	Ordinal
4	Service behavior	Service behavior is a form of behavior that a company or product provider performs to meet the needs of others	1. Form 2. Responsiveness 3. Guarantee 4. Empathy	Ordinal
5	Ease of use	Ease of use is a condition where consumers can use the product without any difficulties caused by the use or consumption of the product	1. Learning 2. Flow suitability 3. Communicative and interactive 4. Hotline/operating manual	Ordinal
6	Consumer decisions	Consumer decisions are a form of selection that has been decided upon by various alternatives created in the minds of consumers	1. Attitude 2. Intention 3. Consumer ability 4. Needs	Ordinal
7	Consumer post-purchase behavior	Post-purchase behavior is a form of behavior that consumers exhibit after the purchase of a product	1. Perception 2. Motivation 3. Personality 4. Culture	Ordinal
8	Consumer trust	Consumer trust is a form of trust that consumers place on a product or company	1. Legality 2. Integrity 3. Goodness 4. Competence	Ordinal
9	Consumer attention	Consumer attention is a form of concern that companies give to their consumers	1. Care 2. Expectancy 3. Product value 4. Appreciation	Ordinal
10	Emotional relationships	Emotional relationships are a form of feeling created by consumers and companies in the use of the product and lasts for a long time	1. Passions 2. Knowledge 3. A sense of belonging 4. Customer experience	Ordinal

Population and Sample

The present study is descriptive in nature, and aims to describe systematically, actually and accurately regarding the facts

and properties of a research object. (Puspowarsito, 2008). The steps of this research work by defining clear and specific objectives and designing the approach

method. The present work is also experimental research, and offers new insights. In experimental research the researchers tested several new variables, which might have a clear effect or not, and might be used in research on other objects. Data collection techniques are a way to get the data used as the basis and support of the research. Techniques used in our research through interviews, questionnaires and library studies. The population for the study is the loyal readers or customers of the "Waspada" newspapers in Medan, where the population is unknown. If the research is to perform a multivariate analysis (for example, correlation or multiple regression), then the sample size is at least 50 times the number of variables studied (Sugiyono, 2016). Accordingly, the sample is estimated at 180 customers who read the Waspada" newspapers in Medan. The sample extraction we used was a nonprobability sampling technique called purposive sampling. Descriptive analysis of this study we used to identify characteristics of respondents who were potential consumers of this study. Data measurement for the

impact analysis we use ordinal data. A structural equation model for impact analysis in our research is as follows.

$$\text{Structural equation; } Y = \alpha + \beta X_1 + \beta X_2 + \beta X_3 + \beta X_4 + \beta X_5 + \beta X_6 + \beta X_7 + \beta X_8 + \beta X_9 + e \text{ (1)}$$

The analysis model used is the stepwise regression analysis model, which determines the magnitude of the relationship of the independent variable to the dependent variable. The range for the research questionnaire is 1 to 6 on the ordinal scale. The determination is to eliminate the neutral content hence the scale of the questionnaire is as follows; absolutely disagree (1); disagree (2); less agree (3); quite agree (4); agree (5) and absolutely agree (6).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results

A social research should test the characteristics of respondents who are the source of research data at the research stage. In this study we used crosstab analysis.

Table 2. Age * level of education (Crosstabulation)

		level of education						Total
		< Junior School	High School	Diploma	Under graduate	Master	Doctoral	
Age	< 15 years	3	0	1	0	0	0	4
	15 -20 years	1	11	2	1	0	0	15
	21 - 30 years	0	20	11	31	0	0	62
	31 - 40 years	0	16	3	33	3	0	55
	41 - 50 years	2	11	2	19	4	1	39
	> 50 years	0	2	0	2	1	0	5
Total		6	60	19	86	8	1	180

The table above it appears to be dominant, with 33 respondents aged 31 to 40 and well-educated (Bachelor). It shows that readers are essentially intellectual adults and therefore the presentation of information should be tailored to this dominant segment, whether in the form of language, narrative or description of information.

Table 3. Other newspapers read besides the "Waspada " newspaper * Age (Crosstabulation)

		Age (Years)						Total
		< 15	15 -20	21 - 30	31 - 40	41 - 50	> 50	
Other newspapers	Analisa	1	3	30	18	16	3	71
	Kompas	1	1	10	13	5	1	31
	Tribun	1	2	10	8	4	0	25
	Sinar Indonesia	1	1	4	1	4	0	11
	Sumut Pos	0	0	2	5	2	0	9
	Andalas	0	3	2	0	1	0	6
	Medan Bisnis	0	0	2	4	0	0	6
	Pos Metro	0	3	1	3	3	0	10
Others	0	2	1	3	4	1	11	
Total		4	15	62	55	39	5	180

The table above it appears that the majority of respondents, 30 respondents aged 21 to 30, read "Analisa" newspapers. It shows that these young readers have a second reading other than the "Waspada" newspaper, namely the "Analisa" newspaper. The distribution of this data also shows that the ability of the "Analisa" newspapers to reach young adult readers with their favorite sections.

		Income (in thousands)					Total
		< Rp. 500	Rp. 500 - Rp. 2.000	Rp. 2.000 - Rp. 5.000	Rp. 5.000 - Rp. 10.000	< Rp. 10.000	
Other newspapers	Analisa	8	9	32	19	3	71
	Kompas	4	8	18	1	0	31
	Tribun	6	4	12	3	0	25
	Sinar Indonesia	2	2	4	3	0	11
	Sumut Pos	2	0	5	2	0	9
	Andalas	3	0	2	1	0	6
	Medan Bisnis	1	3	1	1	0	6
	Pos Metro	3	1	2	4	0	10
	Others	2	2	5	1	1	11
Total		31	29	81	35	4	180

Hypothesis test

Partial test

Table 5. Partial test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.427	1.488		3.648	.000
	Price (X2)	.801	.068	.663	11.811	.000
2	(Constant)	2.407	1.445		1.666	.097
	Price (X2)	.492	.080	.407	6.133	.000
	Product (X1)	.231	.038	.403	6.084	.000
3	(Constant)	1.215	1.417		.858	.392
	Price (X2)	.341	.085	.282	4.000	.000
	Product (X1)	.194	.038	.338	5.144	.000
	Post-purchase behavior (X6)	.266	.066	.264	4.047	.000
4	(Constant)	.262	1.460		.179	.858
	Price (X2)	.309	.086	.256	3.612	.000
	Product (X1)	.170	.039	.296	4.400	.000
	Post-purchase behavior (X6)	.225	.067	.223	3.334	.001
	Service-quality behavior (X3)	.164	.072	.145	2.293	.023
5	(Constant)	-.254	1.461		-.174	.862
	Price (X2)	.281	.085	.233	3.291	.001
	Product (X1)	.145	.040	.253	3.662	.000
	Post-purchase behavior (X6)	.138	.077	.137	1.790	.075
	Service-quality behavior (X3)	.162	.071	.143	2.281	.024
	Emotional relationship (X7)	.192	.085	.173	2.262	.025

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction (Y)

In the table above, it appears that there are five variables that influence using stepwise regression with decision making accepted H_a , rejected H_0 , that means, the value ($t\text{-table} < t\text{-statistics}$) and the significance value < 0.05 . The value of $t\text{-table}$ with degree of freedom is 171 ($n-k / 180 - 9$ independent variables), using the two-way hypothesis test is 1,653. The variables that are significant relationships are as follows. Price (X2) with $t\text{-table}$ value (1,653) $< t\text{-statistics}$ (3,291) and significance value (0,001) < 0.05 . Product (X1) with $t\text{-table}$

value (1,653) $< t\text{-statistics}$ (3,662) and significance value (0,0001) $< 0,05$. Service-quality behavior (X3) with $t\text{-table}$ value (1,653) $< t\text{-statistics}$ (2,281) and significance value (0,024) $< 0,05$. Emotional relationship (X7) with $t\text{-table}$ value (2,262) $< t\text{-statistics}$ (3,291) and significance value (0,025) $< 0,05$. Meanwhile the related variable but insignificant is post-purchase behavior (X6) with $t\text{-table}$ value (1,653) $< t\text{-statistics}$ (1,790) and significance value (0,075) $> 0,05$. It shows that there are five influential variables with details of four

influential and significant variables Price (X2), Product (X1), Service Quality Behavior (X3) and Emotional Relationship (X7), and one influential but insignificant variable is Post-Purchase Behavior (X6).

Coefficient of Determination

That is the ratio of the number of squares regression (SSR) to the total number

of squares (SST). The coefficient is denoted by r^2 or called R Square. Regression Sum of Squares (SSR), Error Sum of Squares (SSE), and Total Sum of Squares (SST) only provide a small interpretation of the variation of regression.

$$\text{Equation} = r^2 = \text{SSR} / \text{SST}$$

Table 6. Model Summary^f

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.663 ^a	.439	.436	4.445	
2	.732 ^b	.536	.531	4.054	
3	.759 ^c	.576	.569	3.889	
4	.767 ^d	.588	.579	3.843	
5	.775 ^e	.600	.588	3.798	1.988
a. Predictors: (Constant), Price (X2)					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Price (X2), Product (X1)					
c. Predictors: (Constant), Price (X2), Product (X1), Post-purchase behavior (X6)					
d. Predictors: (Constant), Price (X2), Product (X1), Post-purchase behavior (X6), Service-quality behavior (X3)					
e. Predictors: (Constant), Price (X2), Product (X1), Post-purchase behavior (X6), Service-quality behavior (X3), Emotional relationship (X7)					
f. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction (Y)					

The table above shows that the value of the adjusted R square (ARS) is 0.588, which means that 58.8% of all independent variables are able to explain the dependent variable or that 58.8% of the regression models in this study can be applied while the remaining 41, 2% was another variable not examined in this study. At a value of 58.8% means that the strength of the regression model is categorized as good in implementation, with an error of 3,798.

Model equation

The model equation is intended to explain the formulation of this research which is simpler and easier to read.

Table 7. Partial t-test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
5	(Constant)	-.254	1.461		-.174	.862
	Price (X2)	.281	.085	.233	3.291	.001
	Product (X1)	.145	.040	.253	3.662	.000
	Post-purchase behavior(X6)	.138	.077	.137	1.790	.075
	Service-quality behavior (X3)	.162	.071	.143	2.281	.024
	Emotional relationship (X7)	.192	.085	.173	2.262	.025
a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction (Y)						

In this study we use standarized coefficients to form regression equations, because running data will work well and there will be no problems in data validation and classical assumption testing. Therefore, the equation of the research regression is as follows.

$$Y = 0.253X1 + 0.233X2 + 0.143X3 + 0.137X6 + 0.173X7 - 3,798$$

The study found that the dominant effect was the product variable (X1) with a value of 0.253, while the smallest influence variable was the service quality behavior variable (X3) with a value of 0.143 and a regression equation error of 3.798, and four variables were not influential and were not included in the regression equation, among others, ease of use (X4), reader decision (X5), trust (X8) and reader attention (X9)

DISCUSSION

The product is related to customer satisfaction

The result of the study found the product variables (X1) with t-table values (1,653) <t-statistics (3,662) and significance values (0.0001) <0.05. It indicates that the product variable (X1) is influential and significant to customer satisfaction (Y) which in this study is the readers of the "Waspada" newspaper.

It indicates that the relationship is a thing of the product can give satisfaction to the consumer. Many dimensions of consumer products consider fulfilling their expectations in order to meet their needs. It would be relatively common consumer perceives a difference between one product and the other depending on who they want to achieve as a result of the fulfillment of their requirements to the product. Tastes are very important because they must be based on and related to the good of the product you want to buy. There is a use value in a product if the value of use increases then the product will also increase (Fikri, Miftah El; Pane, 2018). The "Waspada" newspaper has given their readers a distinctive taste that has made it a distinguishing feature of newspapers. As the oldest and most well-educated newspaper, we focus on information as a movement for change to help people get information about the world, nationally and regionally, which makes consumers fully satisfied with "Waspada" newspaper products.

Price is related to customer satisfaction

The results showed that price variables (X2) with t-table values (1,653) <t-statistics (3,291) and significance values (0.001) <0.05. It shows that the price variable (X2) is influential and significant to customer satisfaction (Y) which in this study is "Waspada" newspaper readers. These results indicate that while prices have a significant impact on customer satisfaction, prices will be a measure of consumer sacrifice converting their resources into money for a product.

Consumers tend to have the size and interpretation of the price set in mind, and the consumer will determine the price elasticity of a product and if the price is affordable then the consumer will be satisfied in sacrificing it. The lower the price of a product, the higher the consumer will want to buy. Instead, the higher the price of a product the lower the consumer is likely to buy. Affordable prices open up competition opportunities (Fikri, 2019). The "Waspada" newspaper is able to maintain its selling price to satisfy its readership and to reduce production costs. Whenever a "Waspada" newspaper wants to raise prices then it needs a complementary strategy such as giving a weekly quiz, or a monthly draw instead of raising the sale price.

Service quality behavior is related to customer satisfaction

In this study, we found a service quality behavior variable (X3) with a t-table value (1,653) <t-statistics (2,281) and a significance value (0.024) <0.05. It shows that the service quality behavior variable (X3) significantly affects customer satisfaction (Y) in the context of "Waspada" Newspaper readers.

These results prove that consumers are very concerned about the behavior of the quality of services performed by salespeople to meet their satisfaction at the process transaction or terminate the exchange of products. Consumers organize and remember the good things they received for interacting with the product through the salesperson or people that mediate products. If the service is provided well, then the consumer will be very satisfied with the service which has implications for product satisfaction. Behavior and purchasing habits have their respective characteristics. These differences in motives and behaviors indicate that the market for this product is heterogeneous with a large number of consumers with varying needs, desires, purchasing capabilities, and purchasing behaviors and demands (Ritonga, Siregar, Fikri, & Agustin, 2018).

In this study, the behavior of service quality is found in the delivery courier, and the newspaper deliveryman who offers and sells the newspaper, a friendly smile and responsiveness to know each consumer that will provide a satisfaction effect for consumers. Because they already know their needs and most likely consumers like this will choose a subscription. If salespeople recognize and understand or memorize the needs of consumers, then consumers will feel they are getting more attention in getting products, therefore the value of the product is better and more valuable.

Post-purchase behavior is related to customer satisfaction

In this study post-purchase behavior variable (X6) with t-table value (1.653) <t-statistic (1.790) and significance value (0.075) > 0.05, indicating that the post-purchase behavior variable (X6) influences, but is not significant to customer satisfaction (Y) which in this study is the reader of Waspada newspaper.

It shows that post-purchase behavior can influence consumers' satisfaction. After purchase a consumer will observe and analyze the products who they have consumed or used. This will have a positive or negative effect on the sustainability of the decision. When consumers receive the positive effects of satisfaction, their post-purchase behavior will make them repeat and keep the product in their heart even leading to the process of loyalty building. This recurring effect will occur in the future. For example, ordering delicious food is not enough to appeal to consumers whose lack of quality of service provided by waiter or waitress, who lack of gracious way of ordering, delivery, and even payment methods made by guests to pay for food already booked so consumers would think twice to revisit the restaurant (Pane, Fikri, & Ritonga, 2018).

In this research, the Waspada newspaper must understand and analyze the consumer behavior that arises after reading the information and buying the news. All

information must be shown the truth, although some truth is difficult to digest its existence for those who occupy opposing positions. Therefore, the Waspada newspaper must be fair in placing an information with a soft and suave language even though it is a truth and all parties who read will only consider it as limited to information and not persuasion.

Emotional relationships are related to customer satisfaction

In this study, the emotional relationship variable (X7) with a t-table value (2,262) <t-statistics (3,291) and a significance value (0.025) <0.05, indicated that the emotional relationship variable (X7) had a significant effect on customer satisfaction (Y) who in this study were readers of Waspada newspapers.

This shows that when a consumer feels the relationship created with the product, it will provide more closeness than just consuming. This closeness will give a satisfied effect in its use as if the consumer is good friends with the product. This relationship is not only true but can also occur digitally with social media. Social media is a media that is friendly and almost owned by all people in the world, the sophistication of features so that it can communicate in both directions broadly makes no restrictions in communication (Fikri, Pane, & Siregar, 2019). If this happens in addition to consumers feeling satisfied, they will also become defenders of the product because of the friendship that has been established. The Waspada newspaper has happened with a lot of interaction between readers on the Waspada Online website, but this needs to be improved by replying to all readers' responses, so that all readers feel cared for and have a special relationship with Waspada.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusions

The main group of concerns we have solved has been addressed and briefly outlined the

solution to the value of this work. The conclusions of this study are;

- The quality of the product has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper.
- Prices have a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper.
- Services behavior have a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper.
- Ease of use has an insignificant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper.
- Consumer decisions has an insignificant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper.
- Post-purchase behavior has an effect but insignificant on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper.
- Emotional relationship has a significant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper
- Consumers trust has an insignificant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper
- Consumers attention has an insignificant effect on customer satisfaction in the context of the Waspada newspaper

Suggestions

Our suggestions are statements that contribute to this work and provide new strategies and future hopes for improvement, discovery and development. Our suggestions for this study are:

- The Waspada newspaper should give differentiation to its products so that they are differentiated from other newspapers, for example analysis. By re-analyzing the core business and pay attention to segments that must be prioritized in the newspaper
- The Waspada newspaper should educate newspaper operators and newspaper vendors to show friendly attitudes towards consumers / readers, so that they have an emotional attachment

between the reader and the Waspada newspaper.

- Waspada Newspapers should grow customer service that is integrated with Waspada Online, besides customers can comment but can also contact directly, or some readers may want to write in Waspada newspapers.
- The Waspada newspaper should take care of every consumer's responses and complaints in polite language that makes its readers like every response that is generated and gives an attractive effect and will be the sustainability of the relationship in the future.

REFERENCE

1. Fikri, Miftah El; Pane, D. N. (2018). Analysis of marketing strategy on purchase decision of ac mitsubishi electric product by consumer in pt . Mitsubishi electric. International Conference 1st and Callpapers Ikatan Sarjana Ekonomi Indonesia Komisariat UNPAB, (Agustus), 6–16. Medan: ISEI Komisariat UNPAB.
2. Fikri, M. El. (2019). Analisis citra merek, harga, distribusi dan promosi terhadap keputusan pembelian produk sunlight oleh konsumen rumah tangga di kota medan (studi kasus di kecamatan medan polonia). *Jurnal Manajemen Tools*, 10(2), 109–124. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
3. Fikri, M. El, Pane, D. N., & Siregar, N. (2019). Memasarkan objek pariwisata kota medan melalui media sosial untuk menaikkan minat kunjungan dan menghapus paradigma negatif. *Jurnal Manajemen Tools*, 11(2), 69–79. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
4. Lupiyoadi, Rambat; Hamdani, A. (2013). *Manajemen Pemasaran Jasa* (3rd ed.). Jakarta: Erlangga.
5. Pane, D. N., Fikri, M. EL, & Ritonga, H. M. (2018). Pengaruh harga dan kualitas pelayanan terhadap kepuasan pelanggan pada rumah makan sidempuan No Title. *Jurnal Manajemen Tools*, 9(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>

6. Puspowarsito, A. H. (2008). Metode Penelitian Organisasi Dengan Aplikasi. Program SPSS. Bandung: Humaniora.
7. Ritonga, H. M., Siregar, N., Fikri, M. El, & Agustin, R. (2018). Manajemen Pemasaran (Konsep dan Strategi). Medan: CV Manhaji.
8. Sugiyono. (2016). Metode Penelitian Manajemen. Bandung: Alfabeta.

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